

STRATEGIES FOR MASTERING THE COMMUNICATIVE STYLE IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The article discusses various strategies for mastering the communicative style in the process of learning a foreign language. The main attention is paid to the importance of the formation of communicative competence as a key component of successful language learning. The methods and approaches aimed at developing communication skills are analyzed, including role-playing games, modeling real situations, working in groups and individual tasks. Special attention is paid to the adaptation of communication styles to the cultural and sociolinguistic features of the studied language. The authors emphasize the need to integrate such strategies into the educational process in order to increase the effectiveness of learning a foreign language and improve intercultural interaction.

Keywords: Communication competence, teaching a foreign language, communication style, intercultural communication, learning strategies, interactive methods, adaptation of communication styles, role-playing games, multimedia resources, autonomous learning.

Introduction

In the modern world, proficiency in a foreign language is becoming an important skill necessary for effective intercultural interaction. However, as noted by renowned linguist Michael Cunningham, successful language learning requires not only knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, but also mastery of a communicative style that defines ways of communication and adaptation in various cultural contexts. This article explores strategies aimed at developing communicative competence in the process of learning a foreign language. Interactive methods such as role-playing games and simulations of real situations are considered, as well as individual approaches that contribute to the successful application of language in practice and improve intercultural skills.

Materials and types of research

This study is aimed at studying the most effective strategies and tools for developing a communicative style among foreign language learners. The research was conducted to achieve three goals: (1) to study effective strategies for mastering a communicative style: to analyze various methods and approaches that contribute to the development of communicative competence in learning a foreign language, such as interactive classes, role-playing games, multimedia resources and intercultural interaction, (2) to develop intercultural awareness: to explore how the features of the cultural context they influence the formation of a communication style, and how teachers can integrate knowledge about cultural differences into the learning process to improve communication effectiveness, (3) to determine how autonomous learning methods, such as the independent use of multimedia resources and practical interaction with native speakers, help students develop communication skills and adapt to various communicative situations.

In the context of globalization and expanding intercultural interaction, foreign language proficiency is becoming one of the most important competencies of a modern person. However, successful language learning implies not only mastering its grammatical structure

and lexical stock, but also the development of communicative competence, which allows effective interaction with native speakers in various social and cultural contexts. The communicative style, which determines the manner of communication, forms of expression of thoughts and interaction strategies, becomes a central element in the process of learning a foreign language.

The purpose of this article is to study strategies for mastering a communicative style in the process of learning a foreign language. The importance of this aspect is due to the fact that communication skills directly affect a person's ability to adapt to a different cultural environment and successfully apply language in real life situations. The article will consider a wide range of methods aimed at developing communicative competence, including interactive approaches such as role-playing games, simulation of real situations and group work. Attention will also be paid to individual learning strategies and the influence of cultural characteristics on the formation of a communication style. [1, 45p.].

Aimagambetova K. A. is a Kazakhstani methodologist, in her works emphasizes the importance of a communicative approach to teaching foreign languages, pointing out that "language acquisition should occur not only through the study of grammatical structures, but also through active interaction in real communicative situations. This allows students to adapt to different communication contexts and develop thinking flexibility". [2, 5p.].

A lot of research has been conducted in linguistics and related fields of knowledge, which have prepared a significant theoretical basis for successfully solving the issue of forming strategies for the communicative style of British linguoculture in foreign language practice classes (T.N. Astafurova, V.V. Vorobyov, J.A. Gorodetskaya, G.V. Elizarova, I.L. Pluzhnik, O.S. Issers, Y.B. Kuzmenkova, J.B. Kulikova, T.V. Larina, O.A. Leontovich, Y.E. Prokhorov, V.V. Safonova, I.A. Sternin, P.V. Sysoev, V.P. Furmanova, M. Byram, J. Corbet, etc.).

One of the Kazakhstani authors who wrote about strategies for the development of spoken language in

English is Smanova Zhanar Muratovna. In her work, she focuses on methods and strategies aimed at developing oral speech among English language learners. In particular, in her research, she emphasizes the importance of a communicative approach and active learning methods that promote the development of conversational skills.

In the journal "Education and Innovation" she published "The development of oral speech in English using interactive methods". In this study, Smanova describes in detail how interactive activities such as role-playing and debate contribute to the development of students' conversational skills, increasing their self-confidence and motivation to learn a language.

There, Smanova describes the main strategies such as:

- Role-playing game is a method in which students practice speaking by acting out various scenarios of communication in English.
- Group discussions and debates that help students improve their argumentation skills and develop fluency of speech.
- Simulation of real situations, in which students are immersed in situations close to real life, where they must communicate in English.
- Using authentic materials such as movies, news and podcasts in English, which helps students get used to natural speech and expand their vocabulary.

Smanova J. M. emphasizes that a key aspect of the development of spoken language is regular practice and the creation of a motivating environment where students can freely express their thoughts in English without fear of making mistakes. [3, 22-25p.].

Thus, the relevance of the research lies in the need to develop effective methods and strategies for deeper development of the communicative style when learning a foreign language, which will improve the quality of education and increase the level of language proficiency in various spheres of life.

In the modern world, proficiency in a foreign language is becoming an important skill necessary for effective intercultural interaction. However, successful language learning requires not only knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, but also mastery of a communicative style that defines ways of communication and adaptation in various cultural contexts. This article explores strategies aimed at developing communicative competence in the process of learning a foreign language. Interactive methods such as role-playing games and simulations of real situations are considered, as well as individual approaches that contribute to the successful application of language in practice and improve intercultural skills. [4, 55p.].

Strategies that most effectively contribute to mastering the communicative style when learning a foreign language.

B. K. Yessimzhanova, a researcher in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, states: "The communicative approach requires teachers to create educational situations where students can not just memorize new words and phrases, but use them in practical activities, modeling everyday dialogues and tasks. Only

through such active practice can one achieve true mastery of the language". [5, 8p.].

Effective mastery of the communicative style requires the use of a variety of strategies that allow students not only to learn the language at the level of vocabulary and grammar, but also to learn how to apply it in real communicative situations. The most effective of them are:

Interactive learning methods

Role-playing games and simulations allow students to reproduce real-life situations, which helps to better understand and master the social and cultural contexts of communication. Such methods give students the opportunity to use language in various scenarios, developing the ability to adapt their communication strategies depending on the circumstances. For example, acting out situations of everyday life or business meetings helps to consolidate communication skills, allowing students to get used to the language turns and communication manners characteristic of native speakers.

Group work and paired assignments

Working in groups and pairs provides students with the opportunity to interact with others, exchange opinions and practice dialogue in an environment close to reality. This method not only develops oral speech skills, but also improves the perception of language by ear, which contributes to the formation of a more flexible and dynamic communicative style. In the process of group discussions, students learn to adapt to the communication styles of their partners, which brings them closer to the real practice of communication in a multilingual environment.

Use of multimedia resources

Multimedia resources such as videos, podcasts and audio materials with native speakers allow students to immerse themselves in an authentic language environment. This helps them to better understand the cultural and stylistic features of communication in the language they are learning. The use of such resources helps to improve the perception of language in dynamics, including intonation and non-verbal aspects of communication, which is important for the formation of a full-fledged communicative style.

Intercultural awareness and learning

Knowledge of the cultural characteristics of communication helps students to interpret the language correctly and avoid communication barriers. The inclusion of intercultural awareness in the educational process contributes to the development of students' ability to adapt their communication strategies depending on the cultural norms characteristic of native speakers. This may include studying differences in the use of formalities, the expression of emotions, and non-verbal gestures, which significantly improves students' communicative competence. [6, 15p.].

These strategies not only improve students' language skills, but also help them develop the flexible and adaptive communication style necessary for successful communication in various social and cultural contexts.

The influence of cultural characteristics on the choice and use of communication strategies in the learning process.

Kurmanalieva Sh. T. is a teacher and researcher, in her writings emphasizes the importance of intercultural competence: "Mastering a foreign language is impossible without taking into account cultural differences. For successful communication, it is necessary to teach students not only language norms, but also the peculiarities of behavior and thinking of native speakers in order to avoid misunderstandings and conflicts in real communication". [7, 12p.].

Cultural characteristics play a key role in the formation of a communicative style, and their influence on the choice and use of foreign language teaching strategies cannot be underestimated. Language is closely related to culture, as it not only conveys information, but also reflects the values, norms and traditions of a particular society. In this context, the study of cultural differences becomes necessary for the successful acquisition of a foreign language. The influence of cultural factors on communication strategies is manifested in the following aspects:

Formality and the level of distance in communication

In different cultures, the norms of communication can vary significantly in terms of the degree of formality. For example, in Asian cultures such as Japanese or Korean, there is a strong focus on formality and respect for elders, which is manifested in the use of more polite forms of speech and distance in communication. At the same time, in Western cultures, such as American or Australian, the communication style may be less formal and more direct. Students should take these differences into account in order to choose appropriate communication strategies, avoiding awkward situations involving violations of cultural norms.

Non-verbal elements of communication

Cultural differences affect not only the verbal aspects of communication, but also non-verbal ones, such as gestures, facial expressions, eye contact and distance between interlocutors. For example, in some cultures, such as Italian or Spanish, active gestures and physical intimacy in the process of communication are considered the norm, whereas in more restrained cultures, such as the Scandinavian countries, this may be perceived as an invasion of personal space. Students need to know how to use non-verbal elements in accordance with cultural norms so that their communication is more effective. [8, 65p.].

Cultural differences in the perception of time and communication style

Cultures differ in how they perceive time and the pace of communication. For example, in cultures with a monochronous perception of time (Western countries), observing time frames and clear planning are considered important, and the communication process usually goes faster. In polychronic cultures (Latin America, the Middle East), the perception of time is more flexible, and interaction can be slower and focused on building personal relationships. These differences influence the choice of communication strategies, for example, a more formalized and structured approach may be useful in one context, while a more free and informal style of communication will be successful in another.

The use of humor and metaphors

Cultural differences can also influence the interpretation of humor, sarcasm, and metaphors. In some cultures, humor is an important element of communication and can be used to ease tension or strengthen social ties (for example, in the United States or Great Britain), in other cultures it may be considered inappropriate in a formal setting (for example, in Japan or China). Thus, students need to be aware of how native speakers use these elements in their communication so as not to encounter cultural misunderstandings. [9, 104p.].

Gender and gender roles in communication

Cultural norms and expectations regarding gender roles can also influence communication style. In some cultures, communication between men and women is subject to strict rules, and failure to comply with these norms can lead to misunderstandings or conflicts. For example, in some countries of the Middle East, expectations regarding the role of women in communication may differ from Western standards. Understanding these cultural characteristics helps students choose more appropriate interaction strategies in accordance with cultural and social norms.

Research results

The study was designed for middle school students a set of exercises has been developed. The purpose of the developed set of exercises is the formation of speech skills at the middle stage of school training, namely in the 7th grade. The tasks set before the developed set of exercises: this comprehensive research work does not include a complete lesson. Each lesson takes only 10-15 minutes. Thus, we study the formation of speech skills by introducing material from poems and songs from the smallest into the lessons.

The expected result of the use of songs and poems in the study lessons

- The ability to freely use words and phrases to express yourself freely in a foreign language and be able to understand the narrator's statement;
- Development of students' speech, including the enrichment of their vocabulary and the formation of harmonious speech skills;

The solution to these problems is provided by systematic work on the meaning and use of words. It is very important for adolescents to have personal communication with their peers, they are able to understand, analyze and systematize the material, they have a conscious attitude to teaching and are interested in action, we have described a set of exercises with the aim of subordinating their educational activities to a single system that meets their needs. The developed set of exercises will help teachers diversify their classes, thereby increasing the interest and motivation of students in learning English. The research work includes a full practice time. According to the course of work, in the experimental class, one poem or song is considered in each lesson and after it is given exercises to consolidate new words. For the complex of exercises developed by US, 18 verse and song materials were selected, the texts of which contain lexical materials that are taught in high school. For each of the 9 Sections, 2 song or poem materials are offered, after listening to which

students should perform exercises aimed at strengthening lexical skills and fully understanding the meaning of the song or poem material. To better understand the meaning of the first song, the subtitle is provided along with the videos. Listening to the material and watching a parallel video reveals the essence of a poem or song. In a certain thematic section of the textbook, a number of questions are proposed that work out the given vocabulary. Material is presented in the form of a second audio recording. In the tasks dedicated to it, in addition to auxiliary questions, such types of exercises are performed as entering missing words after listening to audio material. The collection presents speech exercises aimed at solving communicative and cognitive problems, as well as exercises for replacing letters. On the basis of each song, a task is developed aimed at the formation and consolidation of lexical skills after listening to audio materials.

At the initial stage, watching videos with subtitles for the song. The second hearing is not recommended. However, if, according to the teacher's assessment, the level of students' understanding of the material is unsatisfactory, then it is advisable to repeat the listening after the first question in the task. Next, we proceed directly to the task, which includes five questions. Students briefly recite the content of the song, highlight the meaning and meaning of the text they hear, and reinforce their example with lexical units heard in the song. Through the next question, students deepen the meaning of the material and present their arguments and thoughts using vocabulary from songs and poems. Then the students' attention test. The next question suggests that students, using their imagination and knowledge, independently explain the meaning of the given expressions and formulate their definitions. The last point is aimed at the formation of students' fluency with words and examples from personal experience. Material is presented in the form of a second audio recording. In the tasks dedicated to it, in addition to auxiliary questions, such types of exercises are performed as entering missing words after listening to audio material. Students are given handouts in the form of sheets with lyrics in which they need to enter the Lost Words. This type of task requires re-listening to independently check the entered words. Further, a joint verification of the work is carried out, then a discussion of difficult words and their elaboration. The exercise is aimed at developing students' vocabulary, the ability to recognize the learned lexical units and write them correctly.

The experimental study was conducted in the municipal state institution "General Education Kazakh secondary school named after Kadyr Mirza Ali" of the Department of Education of the akimat of West Kazakhstan region. The experiment involved 7th grade students from 21 people. The experiment was carried out using poems and songs.

The experiment was carried out for 7 classes. There were 11 people in the first control group and 10 in the second experimental group. In the first group, we conducted a lesson with a traditional form of training, and in the second group, a lesson was held using poems and songs. The class performance of the first group is higher than that of the second group.

Brief description of groups:

1 subgroup (traditional training group). The vast majority of students are distinguished by high cognitive activity, are always ready for classes and try to score high points during the lesson. However, there are a few students in the group who lag behind the rest.

2 subgroups (experimental group). Among the students there are several children who are adapted to learning and acquiring new knowledge, but the bulk of them do not differ in activity and productivity. In this younger group, children often come with unprepared homework, in the lesson they work slowly and without enthusiasm.

The second stage. Formative stage. The control group studied according to the curriculum developed jointly with the subject teacher. In the process of working with the experimental group, a set of exercises based on the song material created during this study was used. The lesson with the experimental group was built on the basis of the topic "Playing games" in the 6th chapter, where it is recommended to study vocabulary on games and computers. The following audio recordings are recommended for this chapter: 6.1. "Epic Rap Battle: Nerd" Vs "Geek" and 6.2. "Bad Religion – I love my computer".

The first stage of working on the exercise was watching videos with subtitles for the song. Then he was given tasks. Students briefly recounted the content of the song, highlighted the meaning and meaning of the text they heard. Through the next question, students deeply delved into the meaning of the song and expressed their thoughts on a given topic using thematic vocabulary. Next, the students found the games mentioned in the lyrics of the song, and also told about their favorite computer games. In addition, the students independently explained the meaning of the song. With the help of a teacher, he discovered the meaning of words. Also, students independently explained the meaning of new words and formulated definitions of concepts via the internet. At the final stage of working with the exercise, the students expressed their opinions on the task and proved them with examples from personal experience, which resulted in a small discussion. Working on the second song, listening to "Bad Religion – I love my computer", listening to the track and filling in the blanks in the lyrics of the song. Students received tasks with the text of the song, in which they need to enter the missing words. The song was listened to again, and then a joint check of the results of the work was carried out, and then work was carried out to discuss unfamiliar words and decipher their meaning.

The third stage. The intermediate stage. At the final stage of the experiment, both groups were given the task of writing an essay on the topic "My favorite computer game" during the lesson. During the examination of the essays, 2 grades were set: for literacy and content. As a result, the following results were obtained, which are presented below. From the table it can be seen that the average score is low, despite the fact that this group was students who perfectly mastered the material studied and successfully used it in their work. Based on the indicators of the diagram, we can conclude that the experimental group showed high results.

Although the difference is only 0.4 points in terms of average literacy and 0.3 points in terms of content, it should be noted that the experimental group initially showed low results throughout the course of study. Because of this, even such a slight gap is developed exercises for the formation of lexical skills based on song material gives reason to prove the effectiveness of using the set.

The fourth stage. Conducting final testing. A control test was chosen as the final Test . It was necessary to score a maximum of 60 points. Based on the indicators of the tables, it should be noted that the control group has a greater number of "satisfactory" grades compared to the experimental group, but the same number of "excellent" grades. In the experimental group, the vast majority of students received a "good" rating, which indicates the success and consolidation of the topic "Playing Games". Chart data show that the difference is 0.2 points, which indicates that it is more profitable to use poems and songs to form lexical skills with song material.

Conclusion

Mastering a communicative style in the process of learning a foreign language is a complex and multifaceted task that requires a combination of various pedagogical strategies. One of the key goals of learning is not just to transfer knowledge about grammar and vocabulary, but also to develop the ability to use language in real communicative situations. In this context, approaches such as communication-oriented learning, the use of authentic texts and materials, as well as modeling real dialogues and situations in which students can apply their knowledge in practice play a special role.

In addition, effective mastery of the communicative style includes not only the development of verbal skills, but also an understanding of cultural and social norms of communication in the target language. Intercultural competence allows students to better understand the contexts and nuances of communication, which makes their speech not only correct, but also appropriate in specific situations. Strategies aimed at integrating intercultural aspects significantly increase the ability to successfully interact with native speakers.

It is also important to take into account the individual needs and characteristics of students. The adaptation of teaching methods to the level of training, cognitive styles and motivation of students contributes to the creation of a comfortable and supportive educational environment. This, in turn, helps to develop students' autonomy, giving them the opportunity to manage their learning process more effectively and consciously.

Thus, mastering the communicative style in a foreign language requires an integrated approach combining cognitive, cultural and practical dimensions. The application of these strategies makes it possible to create conditions for deep immersion in the language and its successful use in real life, which is the basis for the formation of full-fledged intercultural communication skills in the global world.

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